

THE EFFECT OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-ESTEEM TO LIFE SATISFACTION IN NURSES

HEMŞİRELERDE MESLEKİ ÖZSAYGININ YAŞAM MEMNUNİYETİNE ETKİSİ

Rukiye DEMİR DIKMEN ¹, Hacı Yusuf GÜLEÇ ², Hakime ASLAN ³

¹Bingol University Healthcare Vocational School, Bingol, Türkiye

²Kilis 7 Aralık University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Kilis, Türkiye

³Inonu University, Faculty of Nursing, Malatya, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

Objective: This research was conducted to examine the effect of nurses' professional self-esteem on life satisfaction.

Materials and Methods: This is a descriptive study. It was conducted with 141 nurses working in a state hospital. The data were collected with the "Personal Information Form", "Professional Self-Esteem Scale (PSS)" and "Life Satisfaction Scale (SWLS)".

Results: The mean age of the participant nurses was 29.38±6.99 years. The mean score of the nurses from the "Positive emotions" sub-dimension of PSS was 49.05±10.44, the mean score of the "Negative emotions" sub-dimension was 52.54±12.34, and the total mean of the MSDS was 101.60±21.79; The mean score they got from the SWLS was determined as 13.13±4.42. It was detected that there was a moderately significant positive correlation between professional self-esteem and life satisfaction in nurses (r: .477, p<0.01). It was determined that there was a moderately significant positive relationship between the positive emotions and negative emotions about the profession and life satisfaction. It has been determined that as professional self-esteem increases, life satisfaction also increases.

Conclusion: It has been determined that professional self-esteem positively affects life satisfaction.

Keywords: Professional Self-esteem, Life satisfaction, Nursing

ÖZET

Amaç: Bu araştırma, hemşirelerin mesleki öz saygısının yaşam memnuniyeti üzerindeki etkisini incelemek amacıyla yapılmıştır.

Gereç ve Yöntemler: Bu, tanımlayıcı bir çalışmadır. Bir devlet hastanesinde çalışan 141 hemşire ile gerçekleştirilmiştir. Veriler, "Kişisel Bilgi Formu", "Mesleki Öz Saygı Ölçeği (PSS)" ve "Yaşam Memnuniyeti Ölçeği (SWLS)" ile toplanmıştır.

Bulgular: Katılımcı hemşirelerin ortalama yaşı 29,38±6,99 yıldır. Hemşirelerin PSS'nin "Pozitif duygular" alt boyutundan aldıkları ortalama puan 49,05±10,44, "Negatif duygular" alt boyutundan aldıkları ortalama puan 52,54±12,34 ve SWLS'nin toplam ortalama puanı 101,60±21,79'dur; SWLS'den aldıkları ortalama puan ise 13,13±4,42 olarak belirlenmiştir. Hemşirelerde mesleki öz saygı ile yaşam memnuniyeti arasında orta derecede anlamlı pozitif bir korelasyon (r: .477, p<0.01) olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Mesleğe ilişkin olumlu ve olumsuz duygular ile yaşam memnuniyeti arasında orta derecede anlamlı pozitif bir ilişki olduğu belirlenmiştir. Mesleki öz saygı arttıkça yaşam memnuniyetinin de arttığı tespit edilmiştir.

Sonuç: Mesleki öz saygının yaşam memnuniyetini olumlu yönde etkilediği belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Mesleki Öz Saygı, Yaşam Memnuniyeti, Hemşirelik

Sorumlu Yazar: Rukiye DEMİR DIKMEN, Bingol University Healthcare Vocational School, Bingol, Türkiye

E-mail: rukiyedemir2015@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Occupation is an important element that enables individuals to find a place for themselves in social life, helps them express themselves and gains prestige. Personality traits of individuals and their suitability for the profession they work in are necessary for them to be successful in their profession (Şener et al., 2011; Erden et al., 2014). The fact that individuals acquire professions suitable for their own personality and character and have positive attitudes towards their profession also contributes to a happy life. In order to achieve this, individuals need to have positive professional self-esteem (Çetinkaya et al., 2016; Kahraman et al., 2021). Professional self-esteem is known as individuals' acceptance of their professional responsibilities and personal value judgments regarding their profession (Kahraman et al., 2021). It is very important for nurses to increase their nursing knowledge, skills and experience in order to fulfill their duties effectively, to increase their strong nursing values and professional self-esteem as a professional, to provide reliable patient care (Kahraman et al., 2021; Kim, 2011).

Adequately developed professional self-esteem can support individual autonomy and professional self-confidence. It can also contribute to effective communication skills. It is assumed that these will contribute to the increase of job satisfaction (Kabeel et al., 2017). Job satisfaction and life satisfaction are considered to be two concepts that go into each other, complement each other, and make sense of each other (Dikmen, 1995). Life satisfaction; It expresses the taste that an individual takes from his life in every aspect. For this reason, it is very important that the satisfaction he receives in both his private and business life will naturally reflect on the life energy of the individual and affect his whole life positively or negatively (Kaplan, 2014).

Unhappiness, dissatisfaction, reluctance, unfulfillment of expectations and disappointment in business life affect the general life of individuals as well as reduce life satisfaction (Keser, 2011). It is possible to say that life satisfaction of nurses who work in environments where stress factors are intense and job satisfaction cannot be achieved may be negatively affected (Avşaroğlu et al., 2005). Studies in the literature report that there are many personal and work-related factors that affect nurses' life satisfaction. In a study conducted with Korean nurses, it was found that high personal achievement, low emotional exhaustion, the fact that nurses are satisfied with their profession and not working at night increases their life satisfaction (Lee et al., 2004). At the same time, it has been determined that there is generally a moderate positive relationship between self-esteem and life satisfaction in nurses and/or nursing students (Kim et al., 2018; Kupcewicz, 2020; Kupcewicz, 2020). In a study conducted in China, it was determined that there is a close relationship between self-esteem and life satisfaction for both women and men (Farwa et al., 2019). Studies examining the relationship between professional self-esteem and life satisfaction were found to be insufficient in the literature. This research was carried out to evaluate the effect of nurses' professional self-esteem on life satisfaction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of Study: The study was conducted in a cross-sectional design.

Sample of the Research: The study was conducted in a cross-sectional design.

The population of the research consisted of 220 nurses working in a state hospital. The study did not use a sample size; it aimed to reach the entire population. Nurses who did not want to participate in the study, worked in the institution for less than three months, were on leave, and filled the data collection form incompletely or incorrectly were excluded from the study. The research was completed with the participation of 141 nurses. 64% of the universe has been reached. Research data was collected online between 2020 and 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Data Collection and Instruments

Personal Information Form

In this form, there are 7 closed-ended questions that include nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and information about the profession.

Professional Self-Esteem Scale (PSS): This scale, which was developed by Arıcak in 1999, is a 5-point Likert-type scale that aims to measure the respect attitudes of individuals working in a profession. 14 of these items contain positive statements and 16 of them contain negative statements. The total score of the scale varies between 30 and 150. High scores obtained from the scale indicate high professional self-esteem (Arıcak, 1999). The Cronbach's alpha value of the scale for this study was found to be 0.94.

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS): It is a seven-item Likert-type scale developed by Diener et al., which determines the life satisfaction of individuals (Diener, 1985). As a result this scale validity and reliability study conducted by Dağlı and Baysal in 2016 (Kim, 2011). In the analysis, the scores of the scale are minimum 5 and maximum 25. High scores obtained from the scale indicate high life satisfaction (Dağlı et al., 2016). In this study, the Cronbach's alpha value was 0.87.

Data Analysis: Statistical analysis of the data in the study was carried out in the SPSS 25 (Statistical Package for Social Science) package program. The socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses and the opinions of the nurses about their professional self-esteem and life satisfaction were given as numbers and percentages, and the scores obtained from the scales were given as mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values. In the analysis of the data obtained in the study, the normality of the data distribution was first examined using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov/Shapiro-Wilk test; skewness and kurtosis values were also checked. Parametric tests were used in the analysis of data showing a normal distribution and homogeneous variances. For data that did not meet the assumption of normal distribution and/or were at the ordinal scale level, non-parametric tests such as the Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis H tests were used. The significance level was accepted as $p < 0.05$ in the analyses.

Ethical Approval: Ethics committee has been got approval (92342550/044) from Bingol University Ethics Committee and written institutional permission from Provincial Health Directorate before collecting research data.

RESULTS

The average age of the participants is 29.38 ± 6.99 years. 77.3% of them were female and 51.1% of them were single. It was determined that 58.9% of the nurses had graduated from a university, 29.1% had 1-5 years of professional experience, 73.8% worked as service nurses, and 55.3% received regular in-service training (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of nurses according to their sociodemographic characteristics

Features	Number (n)		Percent
		(%)	
Age	29.38±6.99		
Gender	Woman	109	77.3
	Male	32	22.7
Marital status	Single	72	51.1
	Married	69	48.9
Education level	High school	15	10.6
	Associate degree	22	15.6

	Bachelor's degree	83	58.9
	Graduate	21	14.9
Professional experience period	0-1 years	28	19.9
	1-5 years	41	29.1
	5-10 years	37	26.2
	10-20 years	24	17.0
	20 years and above	11	7.8
Position	Service nurse	104	73.8
	Executive nurse	21	14.9
	Other (ECG, blood collection nurse, etc.)	16	11.3
Regular in-service training status	Yes	78	55.3
	No	63	44.7

It was determined that the mean score of the nurses from the "Positive emotions" sub-dimension of MSDS was 49.05 ± 10.44 , the mean score of the "Negative emotions" sub-dimension was 52.54 ± 12.34 , and the total mean of the MSDS was 101.60 ± 21.79 . It was determined that the mean score of the nurses from the SWLS was 13.13 ± 4.42 and their life satisfaction was moderate (Table 2).

Table 2. The mean scores of nurses' PSS and SWLS

	X \pm SS	Min.-Max.	Scale	Score
			Range	
Positive Emotions	49.05 \pm 10.44	14.00-69.00	14.00-70.00	
Negative Emotions	52.54 \pm 12.34	17.00-79.00	16.00-80.00	
Professional Self-Esteem Scale Total	101.60 \pm 21.79	34.00-146.00	30.00-150.00	
Satisfaction With Life Scale Total	13.13 \pm 4.42	5.00-25.00	5.00-25.00	

X: Mean, SS: Standard deviation

A statistically significant difference was found between the PSS "Negative emotions" sub-dimension and the total mean score of SWLS ($p < 0.05$). It was determined that nurses with a professional experience of 0-1 years had a higher mean score in PSS than the other groups. It has been determined that nurses with 5-10 years of professional experience have a higher mean score in PSS than other groups. Determined a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between nurses' regular in-service training and the mean score of the PSS "Positive emotions" sub-dimension (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of nurses' professional self-esteem and life satisfaction with socio-demographic characteristics

Features		Positive Emotions	Negative Emotions	PSS Total	SWLS
Age	X \pm SS (29.38 \pm 6.9)	r=-.057 p=.499	r=.083 p=.326	r=.027 p=.749	r=.016 p=.847
Gender	Woman	48.78 \pm 10.07	52.39 \pm 12.18	101.18 \pm 21.17	13.11 \pm 4.36
	Male	49.96 \pm 11.75	53.06 \pm 13.06	103.03 \pm 24.08	13.18 \pm 4.67
		U=1602.00 p=.484	U=1716.00 p=.890	U=1667.50 p=.706	t=-.076 p=.939
Marital status	single	49.12 \pm 10.39	52.75 \pm 12.41	101.87 \pm 21.79	12.45 \pm 4.38
	married	48.98 \pm 10.58	52.33 \pm 12.35	101.31 \pm 21.94	13.84 \pm 4.37

		U=2484.00 p=.950	U=2471.00 p=.957	U=2463.00 p=.931	t=-1.872 p=.063
Education level	High school	52.60±8.56	56.46±10.06	109.06±17.87	11.53±4.35
	Associate degree	50.50±8.65	55.04±11.12	105.54±18.13	12.54±3.37
	Bachelor's degree	48.49±10.71	51.69±12.56	100.19±22.20	13.20±4.41
	Master's degree	47.23±12.13	50.47±13.89	97.71±25.52	14.61±5.18
		KW=2.251 p=.522	KW=2.628 p=.453	KW=2.375 p=.498	F=1.603 p=.192
Professional experience period	0-1 years	53.32±5.57	56.10±9.88	109.42±14.07	13.85±4.53
	1-5 years	46.70±11.74	48.00±13.68	94.70±24.47	12.17±3.62
	5-10 years	48.18±12.30	53.05±12.95	101.24±24.75	14.59±5.12
	10-20 years	49.33±8.31	54.08±10.78	103.41±18.03	12.83±3.42
	20 years and above	49.27±10.58	55.36±10.68	104.63±19.48	10.63±4.88
		KW=8.125 p=.087	KW=10.111 p=.039*	KW=9.354 p=.053	F=2.716 p=.032*
Position	Service nurse	48.76±10.40	51.98±11.87	100.75±21.28	13.05±4.36
	Executive nurse	49.57±12.03	53.95±13.30	103.52±24.60	13.90±4.64
	Other (ecg, blood collection nurse, etc.)	50.25±8.98	54.37±14.48	104.62±22.26	12.62±4.64
		KW=.366 p=.833	KW=1.211 p=.546	KW=.762 p=.683	F=.437 p=.647
Regular in-service training status	Yes	50.78±10.48	54.35±11.97	105.14±21.35	13.74±4.56
	No	46.92±10.07	50.30±12.52	97.22±21.70	12.38±4.15
		U=1893.50 p=.019*	U=2032.500 p=.078	U=1988.50 p=.052	t=1.835 p=.069

X: Mean, SS: Standard deviation, r: Correlation, KW: Kruskal-Wallis Test, U: Mann-Whitney U Test

It was determined that there was a moderately significant positive correlation between professional self-esteem and life satisfaction in nurses ($r: .477, p<0.01$). It was determined that there was a moderately positive ($r: .505, r: .415, p<0.05$) significant relationship between the sub-scales of positive emotions and negative emotions related to the profession and life satisfaction (Table 4).

Table 4. The relationship between professional self-esteem and life satisfaction in nurses

	Correlation				
		PSSPositive Emotions	PSSNegative Emotions	PSS Total	SWLS
PSS Positive Emotions	r	1			
	p				
PSS Negative Emotions	r	.827**	1		
	p	.000			
PSS Total	r	.948**	.963**	1	
	p	.000	.000		
SWLS	r	.505**	.415**	.477**	1
	p	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). r: correlation.

In Table 5, the effect of Professional Self-Esteem Scale (PSS) on Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) was analyzed by regression analysis. Regression assumptions were tested prior to the analysis. The Shapiro-Wilk test performed on the regression residuals showed no

significant deviation from normality ($p > .05$). As the dependent variable; The total score of LDS was used as the independent variable, and the total score of PSS was used. It was determined that professional self-esteem was effective on nurses' life satisfaction and it was found that $R=.477$, Adjusted $R^2=.222$. It was determined that 22.2% of the total variance in the dependent variable of SWLS was explained by PSS and the result was statistically significant ($p<0.001$). According to the results of the regression analysis, it was determined that the professional self-esteem of the nurses had a positive effect ($Beta=2.354$) on their life satisfaction (Table 5).

Table 5. Examination of the Effect of Professional Self-Esteem on Life Satisfaction in Nurses with Regression Analysis

Model	Non-standardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient		p	F	Sig	R	Adjusted R ²
	Beta	Standard Error	Beta	t					
Constant	70.689	5.089		13.890	.000				
PSS Total	2.354	.367	.477	6.407	.000	41.050	.000 ^b	.477 ^a	.222

a. Dependent Variable: SWLS total

b. Predictors: (Constant), PSS total

DISCUSSION

In this study, which examined the effect of professional self-esteem on life satisfaction in nurses, it was determined that professional self-esteem was an important factor affecting life satisfaction. Supporting the research result, in the study conducted with nurses, it was determined that there was a positive and significant relationship between professional self-concept and professional satisfaction (Nwafor, 2015). In addition, a study on the self-esteem of nursing students found positive relationships between self-esteem and professional nursing value, problem-solving ability, and career identity (Min et al., 2021). A study (2021) determined that professional self-concept has an effective role in nurses' burnout (Goliroshan et al., 2021). According to the views of nurses, nurse trainers and nursing students in a study conducted with semi-structured interviews in Iran (2020), personal, educational, environmental, and social factors are among the factors affecting self-esteem in nurses (Badiyepymaiejahromi et al., 2020). Life satisfaction and professional self-esteem can be affected by many social and demographic factors. In addition, considering the negative effects of pandemics on nurses, it was seen that the high level of stress they experienced affected their lives and professional self-esteem. The result of this research is thought to be important in terms of increasing life satisfaction with high professional self-esteem. Nurses with high professional self-esteem are more responsible for their patients and their work. In addition, they are more respectful and interested in patients while giving care (Mosayebi et al., 2018). Having a good level of professional self-esteem increases the competence of nurses and helps to improve clinical performance and problem-solving. Thus, the quality of nursing care given increases. On the other hand, nurses with low professional self-concept have less clinical competence and lower professional satisfaction. Therefore, these nurses may have a high level of turnover intention (Badiyepymaie et al., 2015). In this study, it is thought that the increase in the importance given to health workers during the pandemic process and the positive image in the society may be effective in the increase of the professional self-esteem of nurses. However, it is recommended to deal with the subject in depth with more detailed research and qualitative interviews. In this study, it was determined that the level of life satisfaction of nurses was

moderate. In a study investigating the life satisfaction of nurses in Poland (2020), it was determined that the majority of nurses (74.1%) had moderate and low levels of life satisfaction (Bartosiewicz et al., 2020). In a study conducted with nurses and midwives, it was determined that the participants had high and moderate life satisfaction (Uchmanowicz et al., 2019). It is thought that the decrease in life satisfaction of nurses, the intense and tiring working hours during the pandemic process, the difficulty of giving care to infected patients, the losses, and various anxieties may be effective. The results of the study determined that there was no difference between some features such as age, marital status, education level, gender, position and in-service training, and professional self-esteem and life satisfaction. In a study in the literature, there was a statistically significant relationship between age, gender, marital status, having a child, family type, working year, place of residence, education level, unit of work, position and preference for the unit, and professional self-esteem no difference was found (Etinkaya et al., 2016). Occupational self-esteem is a multifaceted idea that expresses the activities of the members of the profession in the work environment and includes the personal qualities of a profession. It is thought that the working environment may affect the fact that demographic variables do not affect professional self-esteem. It was determined that the difference between the professional experience period of the participant nurses and their professional self-esteem was statistically significant. In a study (2017) conducted with the participation of 2165 nurses in Turkey, the difference between the professional experience of nurses and their professional self-esteem was found to be statistically significant. In the same study, it was found that the professional self-esteem scores of nurses with 11 years or more of professional experience were statistically significantly higher (Sabanciogullari et al., 2017). In the study conducted by Allobaney et al. (2022) with nurses, in which the professional experience period of the participants was 12.5 years, no significant difference was found between the period of professional experience and self-esteem (Allobaney et al., 2022). With the increase in professional experience, the respect of nurses for their professional self can increase. This may help to provide better care to the sick-healthy individual. In our research, it is seen that the data obtained about the experience period are compatible with the literature.

CONCLUSION

As a result, nurses are at the forefront of the delivery of health services and their performance greatly affects the quality of health care. This study revealed the relationship between professional self-esteem and life satisfaction in nurses working in a state hospital during the Covid-19 pandemic period. According to the results of this research, it was determined that high professional self-esteem is an important factor that increases life satisfaction. In order to increase the professional self-esteem and life satisfaction of nurses, and reduce their intention to leave, it is recommended to improve the professional conditions, support the development of nurses with in-service training, develop a cooperation culture and inform the institution managers about these issues.

LIMITATIONS

This study has limited generalizability due to single-center security, difficulties in establishing causal relationships due to its cross-sectional design, and potential response bias stemming from the use of self-report-based data collection tools.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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